

A Lightweight Hybrid Sign Language Recognition Model with MobileNetV3, BiLSTM and Attention

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Abstract. We tackle word-level American Sign Language (ASL) recognition with a lightweight hybrid architecture that balances accuracy and deployability. Our model pairs a MobileNetV3-Large backbone for spatial representation with a two-layer BiLSTM for temporal modelling and a Bahdanau attention module for frame-level weighting. To improve robustness, we use a signer-independent protocol on WLASL-300, apply a compact 12-keyframe selection strategy, and integrate data augmentation with label smoothing. Trained end to end, the system achieves a **Top-1** validation accuracy of **67.46%** on WLASL-300 while remaining efficient (**3.62M** parameters, **0.93** GFLOPs, **14.07** MB). On an RTX 4090, mean per-video latency is **1.33** ms with throughput of **751** videos/s and peak memory of **40.09** MB. Attention-weighted visualisation shows that the model focuses on discriminative motion phases, providing qualitative interpretability. Compared with heavier backbones or multimodal pipelines, our approach offers a favourable accuracy–efficiency trade-off, making it well suited to edge and real-time applications.

Keywords: Sign Language Recognition · American Sign Language (ASL) · MobileNetV3 · BiLSTM · Attention Mechanism

1 Introduction

As digitisation and visual computing advance, computational systems for sign language are becoming increasingly important for facilitating communication between Deaf and hard-of-hearing communities and wider society. Sign Language Recognition (SLR) offers a pathway to accessible interaction in education, healthcare, and public services by enabling technology-mediated understanding of signed communication.

This work targets *word-level* SLR, i.e., recognising a single lexical item from a short video clip. In contrast to speech recognition, SLR must jointly model fine-grained spatio-temporal dynamics of hands, body, and facial cues. Word-level SLR is practically valuable but remains challenging due to (i) incomplete spatial feature extraction under occlusion and motion blur, (ii) limited temporal modelling capacity for long-range dependencies, (iii) large model footprints that

hinder real-time and edge deployment, and (iv) unstable training arising from weak augmentation and insufficient regularisation.

Previous approaches commonly adopt Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to extract visual features, with recurrent models (LSTM / BiLSTM) that capture temporal structure [15]. Attention mechanisms have proven to be effective in highlighting informative frames and motion phases [1]. To reduce computation, lightweight backbones such as MobileNetV3 have been introduced to SLR with promising accuracy–efficiency trade-offs [2,13]. However, striking a balance between compact architectures and robust accuracy, particularly under signer-independent evaluation, remains an open problem. Moreover, training strategy choices (data augmentation, label smoothing, thresholding) materially affect stability, yet are often underspecified.

We present a lightweight word-level SLR framework that integrates a MobileNetV3 backbone for spatial representation, a Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) for temporal modelling, and an attention module for frame-level feature fusion. To enhance robustness and generalisation, we employ a suite of image augmentations together with label smoothing during training. All experiments are carried out on the publicly available WLASL-300 dataset using a split *signer-independent* to evaluate real-world transfer.

Contributions.

- A compact word-level SLR architecture combining MobileNetV3, BiLSTM, and attention for effective spatio-temporal modelling.
- A training recipe leveraging targeted augmentations and label smoothing to improve stability and generalisation without inflating model size.
- Comprehensive evaluation on WLASL-300 under a signer-independent protocol, demonstrating a favourable accuracy–efficiency trade-off suitable for real-time and edge scenarios.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 details the model architecture and the training procedure. Section 4 presents experimental setup and results. Section 5 concludes and outlines future directions.

2 Literature Review

Sign Language Recognition (SLR) has progressively shifted from instrumented, sensor-based pipelines to vision-based learning systems, driven by advances in artificial intelligence and computer vision. We review three strands of work: (i) traditional sensor-based approaches, (ii) vision-based deep learning methods (appearance- and pose-based, with temporal modelling and attention), and (iii) lightweight architectures and training strategies for deployability.

2.1 Traditional Sensor-Based Approaches

Early systems relied on instrumented capture using data gloves, inertial measurement units (IMUs), or depth sensors (e.g., Kinect) to measure hand pose and

motion directly. Although these pipelines can produce high accuracy under controlled conditions, they incur substantial hardware cost, require intrusive wearables, and generalise poorly beyond laboratory settings [5,12,14]. Consequently, the field has pivoted towards camera-only, vision-based recognition, which is less invasive and more scalable.

2.2 Vision-Based Deep Learning Methods

Appearance-based features. CNNs such as VGG and ResNet have been used to extract frame-level visual features, but their parameter counts and FLOPs hinder real-time use [1]. Efficiency-oriented families (e.g., MobileNetV2 with depth-wise separable convolutions [12] and MobileNetV3 with SE modules and *h-swish* activations [2,13]) improve the accuracy–efficiency trade-off, enabling on-device inference, yet accuracy can degrade in the presence of occlusion, motion blur, or clutter.

Pose-/skeleton-based features. Pose pipelines leverage 2D/3D keypoints (e.g., MediaPipe hands; 21 landmarks) to reduce input dimensionality and focus on kinematics. They can be highly accurate on small, clean datasets [6], but discarding pixel-level appearance loses fine detail critical for complex configurations, occlusions, or low illumination [5,6]. Graph convolutional networks tailored to skeletal data (e.g., SignGraph) improve relational modelling and often outperform plain CNNs on larger corpora [16], showing promise for compact and generalisable SLR.

Temporal modelling. Recurrent models capture dynamics effectively: LSTM and BiLSTM model temporal dependencies, with bidirectional context typically improving accuracy [1,15]. However, recurrence limits parallelism and is susceptible to gradient decay. Transformer variants strengthen global temporal modelling [12]; examples such as TSPNet combine hierarchical semantics with attention [7]. Their computational overhead and memory footprint, however, complicate lightweight deployment.

Attention mechanisms. Attention helps allocate capacity to informative frames and motion phases, improving both performance and interpretability [1,7,10]. In many works it is appended as an auxiliary module rather than co-designed with the backbone, which can limit gains in overall efficiency and accuracy.

2.3 Directions in Lightweight Modelling and Training Optimisation

Edge-oriented use cases (e.g., mobile or embedded devices) motivate the adoption of compact and computationally efficient architectures. Techniques such as model pruning and channel reallocation can substantially reduce inference cost [14], while pose-only inputs further shrink parameter counts [6], albeit at the expense of discarding potentially informative appearance cues. Among appearance-based models, MobileNetV3 offers a favourable trade-off between

compactness and representational capacity [2,13]. Ultra-low-compute model families, such as MoViNet, further demonstrate that strong throughput can be achieved at very low FLOP budgets [11,14]. These trends reflect a broader shift toward efficiency-aware deep learning, particularly in resource-constrained settings, as also evidenced in mobile robotics applications where lightweight visual models are essential for real-time semantic mapping [17]. In this context, we adopt MobileNetV3 as the spatial backbone to prioritise latency and model size while retaining discriminative appearance information.

Training strategy is equally consequential for achieving robust performance under constrained budgets. Targeted data augmentation techniques, including colour jitter, brightness and contrast adjustment, and spatial transformations, are commonly employed to improve robustness and resilience to domain shift [3]. Label smoothing has also been shown to reduce overconfidence and mitigate overfitting, often stabilising optimisation dynamics [10]. However, prior work typically applies these techniques in isolation. Recent advances in explainability and representation analysis suggest that tighter integration between architectural design, training regularisation, and internal feature dynamics can yield more stable and semantically meaningful representations [18]. Motivated by this perspective, our design combines a lightweight backbone with temporal sequence modelling and attention mechanisms, alongside a calibrated augmentation and label-smoothing regimen, to enhance optimisation stability and generalisation under a signer-independent protocol.

2.4 Summary and research gaps

In summary, although existing studies have advanced the development of SLR from various angles, the following gaps still remain: (1) Some methods are insensitive to model size and lack deployment considerations; (2) Temporal modelling methods are not unified, and some studies only rely on rough strategies such as average pooling; (3) The training process is unstable and prone to overfitting, and there is a lack of systematic optimisation of the training strategy.

2.5 Positioning of this study

This study attempts to address the above issues based on existing results. A lightweight MobileNetV3-based structure is constructed which combines a BiLSTM for processing video timing and a frame-level attention mechanism for improving the model’s ability to perceive key information. Image enhancement and label smoothing strategies are also introduced to improve training robustness and generalisation ability. The model is validated using the WLASL-300 dataset. The word-level recognition task aims to strike a balance between accuracy, structural complexity and training efficiency.

3 Methodology

This section will introduce the describes the methodology of the sign language recognition task, including dataset selection, preprocessing and augmentation, model architecture, training protocol, and evaluation metrics.

3.1 Dataset (WLASL-300)

For the evaluation of our model, we used the word-level American Sign Language (WLASL) dataset. It’s the largest American Sign Language dataset collected by native American signers with different backgrounds and signing styles from multiple websites [8]. It comprises over 2000 words, with 21,083 samples. This dataset is further divided into several subsets containing 100, 300, 1000, and 2000 glosses [9]. This paper experimented on a subset of 300 glosses, with 3667 videos. As shown in Table 1. It’s the ratio split of the WLASL-300 dataset.

Table 1. WLASL-300 splits

Dataset Split	WLASL-300
Training Set	2488
Validation Set	649
Test Set	530

3.2 Data Preprocessing and Data augmentation

In the preprocessing, we extracted 12 keyframe images from each video to capture the key moments of sign language actions. Then the images were uniformly resized to 128×128 pixels and normalised.

In order to observe the generalisability of the model, we compared two sets of training methods:

Basic augmentation(experiment 1): only have resize and normalise.

Advanced augmentation(experiment 2): RandomBrightnessContrast: randomly adjust brightness and contrast (p=0.4). GaussNoise, MotionBlur, and MedianBlur are selected to simulate the noise and blur in the shooting.

3.3 Input frame selection

- **Selection of the number of keyframes:** 12 frames strikes a balance between information retention and computational efficiency, which covers key frames in the action without significantly increasing model overhead. It’s reasonable in terms of GPU memory and training efficiency, ensuring performance and stability.
- **Keyframe selection strategy:** A hybrid sampling strategy instead of purely equal interval sampling. First, keep the first and last frames to capture the start and end states of the action. Second, dynamic sampling based

on motion differences between frames. Calculate the mean square difference value of the grayscale maps of adjacent frames and select the one with the most significant motion variation, represented in Equation 1. Finally, if there are less than 12 frames, use equal interval sampling to make up the difference and ensure a fixed length input.

$$D_t = \frac{1}{HW} \sum_{i=1}^H \sum_{j=1}^W (I_t(i, j) - I_{t+1}(i, j))^2 \quad (1)$$

$I_t(i, j)$ denotes the grayscale value of the pixel at position (i, j) in frame t , and H, W are the height and width of the image, respectively. D_t represents the inter-frame difference metric, which is used as a reference for dynamic sampling.

- **Visual Validation:** As shown in Figure 1, 12 frames are able to completely cover the start, change, end states of the action and avoid redundancy. Compared with 8 and 10 frames, 12 frames can record the details of the action more accurately.

Fig. 1. from top to bottom are sampled 8, 10, 12 and 16 frames

3.4 Model architecture design

As shown in Figure 2, the model’s overall architecture involves the data stream passes through feature extraction, temporal modelling and attention weighting from the input video to the final class prediction.

Fig. 2. model architecture design

To enhance temporal modelling, we employ a two-layer BiLSTM (hidden size 128 per direction, yielding 256-d outputs), with dropout ($p=0.5$) and layer normalisation:

$$y = \gamma \cdot \frac{x - \mu}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon}} + \beta \quad (2)$$

For frame-level weighting, we use Bahdanau-style attention. Given BiLSTM hidden states $h_i \in R^{2H}$ ($H = 128$, so the dimension is 256), the attention score and normalised weights are computed as:

$$e_i = \mathbf{v}^\top \tanh(W\mathbf{h}_i + \mathbf{b}), \alpha_i = \frac{\exp(e_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^T \exp(e_j)} \quad (3)$$

The context vector is obtained as the weighted sum:

$$\mathbf{c} = \sum_{i=1}^T \alpha_i \mathbf{h}_i \quad (4)$$

which emphasises informative frames while suppressing redundancy.

3.5 Training Process and Parameter Settings

Use an end-to-end fine-tuning strategy. No freezing of the pre-trained MobileNetV3 backbone. Jointly trained by MobileNetV3, BiLSTM and Attention module, all parameters are involved in gradient updating. Data loading was performed using PyTorch’s DataLoader for batch loading. The batch size was 8. The optimizer was selected as AdamW, the learning rate was set to $1e-4$ and the weight decay was $1e-4$. 60 rounds of training were performed. An early stopping strategy was used to prevent overfitting. The learning rate scheduling was dynamically adjusted based on the validation set performance. The convergence and generalisation ability of the model is ensured. During training, training and validation losses were monitored to ensure model stability and effectiveness. And experiments are conducted under two augmentation conditions separately to observe

the effect of image perturbation on model stability. As shown in Table 2, lists the detailed training parameter settings.

Table 2. Training Parameter Set

Parameter	Value
Optimizer	AdamW
Initial Learning Rate	1e-4
Weight Decay	1e-4
Learning Rate Scheduler	ReduceLROnPlateau (reduce learning rate when validation set does not improve)
Batch Size	8
Maximum Epochs	60
Early Stopping	Stop training if validation set does not improve for 5 consecutive epochs
Loss Function	CrossEntropyLoss (with Label Smoothing = 0.1)

3.6 Evaluation Methodology and Metrics Selection

Model performance is evaluated by a variety of metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. In addition, a detailed analysis was performed using the confusion matrices and classification reports to identify patterns of model error and room for improvement.

4 Experimental Results and Analysis

4.1 Experimental Results

4.1.1 Accuracy Comparison

Table 3 shows the performance of the two experimental schemes in the training and validation. The results indicate that through data augmentation techniques, the validation accuracy improves from 66.44% to 67.46% (+1.02%), and final training accuracy from 92.89% to 95.94% (+3.05%).

Table 3. Comparison of Training and Validation Accuracy

Metric	Exp1 (Basic)	Exp2 (Augmented)	Difference
Best Val Acc	66.44%	67.46%	+1.02%
Final Train Acc	92.89%	95.94%	+3.05%
Final Val Acc	66.27%	67.29%	+1.02%

4.1.2 Classification Performance Metrics

In addition, accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score were used to evaluate the model on the test set. As shown in Table 4, the enhanced model slightly improves all four metrics, indicating that data augmentation and label smoothing enhance sensitivity to boundary samples and minority classes and improve overall generalisation.

Table 4. Comparison of Performance Metrics

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Experiment 1 (Basic)	0.6644	0.3817	0.3967	0.3771
Experiment 2 (Augmented)	0.6746	0.3963	0.4215	0.3963

4.1.3 Confusion Matrix Analysis

Figure 3 shows the confusion matrices for the base and augmented models. The confusion matrix is used to show the relationship between real labels and predicted labels, and the closer to the diagonal line indicates the more accurate classification.

Experiment1_Basic model predicts most classes accurately, demonstrating good discrimination ability, but a few classes remain weaker, suggesting confusion for gestures with similar shapes or subtle movements.

Experiment2_Augmented shows the confusion matrix of the augmented model, with more balanced classification across categories, indicating stronger generalisation.

4.1.4 Efficiency Analysis

Our final model has only 3.62M parameters and 0.93 GFLOPs, and a compact size of 14.07 MB. On an RTX 4090 GPU, the average inference latency per video is 1.33 ms, the throughput reached 751.07 videos/s, and the peak GPU memory usage is only 40.09 MB. These results demonstrate that the model achieves both structural efficiency and suitability for deployment on resource-limited devices.

4.2 Interpretability Analysis of Model Decisions

- **Interpretable Design of Attention Mechanisms:** The model uses bi-directional LSTM and attention mechanism to make its decision-making process more interpretable. Attentional weights show which keyframes are attended to when the model is making classification decisions. This not only improves the performance of the model but also provides a transparent decision making process.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrices: (left) Experiment1_Basic;(right) Experiment2_Augmented.

- **Attention weight visualisation implementation:** We implement attention-weight visualisation to intuitively show the model’s focus across frames. As shown in Figure 4, higher attention weights align with gesture transitions and peak motion frames, while redundant frames receive lower weights, indicating the model focuses on discriminative moments.
- **How the Attention Mechanism Works:** The bidirectional LSTM processes the input sequence and outputs hidden states of shape $[B, T, 2H]$ (B: batch size; T: time steps; 2H: concatenated hidden size). The attention module softmax-normalizes per-step weights and computes a weighted sum, yielding a global representation for classification that focuses on informative moments.
- **Practical application value and significance:** This interpretable analysis has significant practical value. First, by observing whether the attention weights are as expected (focus on keyframes). It can be verified whether the model has learned meaningful features. Second, when predictions are incorrect, analyzing attention weights helps reveal the cause of errors and guide model improvement. In addition, such analysis can inform architecture optimisation. For example, by adjusting keyframe extraction strategies. Most importantly, an explainable decision-making process enhances user trust in model predictions, which is crucial for real-world adoption.

4.3 Comparison with Existing Techniques

To contextualise our approach, we compare against representative SLR systems spanning appearance- and pose-based inputs, recurrent and Transformer-style temporal modelling, and lightweight vs. heavyweight backbones. Table 5 summarises backbone choice, temporal module, attention usage, dataset/split, and reported Top-1 accuracy.

Fig. 4. attention weight

Several prior works attain strong accuracy by (i) relying on additional modalities (e.g., pose/keypoints or depth), or (ii) adopting structurally complex Transformers. While effective on specific benchmarks, these designs typically incur high computational cost, substantial training resources, and non-trivial deployment constraints (e.g., signer-dependent protocols, larger FLOPs/params). In contrast, our method uses only RGB inputs and a compact MobileNetV3 backbone with a BiLSTM and Bahdanau attention, yielding an accuracy–efficiency profile that is well suited to real-time and edge scenarios.

Under the stricter *signer-independent* protocol on WLASL-300, our model achieves a Top-1 accuracy of **67.46%** with **3.62 M** parameters and **0.93 GFLOPs**. This compares favourably to methods reporting on easier signer-dependent settings or smaller WLASL subsets (e.g., 100/1000) and demonstrates a state-of-the-art *efficiency–accuracy trade-off* in the sub-1 GFLOP regime. The result underscores that careful pairing of a lightweight spatial backbone with targeted temporal modelling and attention can match or exceed the practical utility of more complex, resource-intensive pipelines.

Table 5. Comparison with representative SLR methods. Results are reported as given in the original papers; benchmarks and evaluation protocols differ (*e.g.*, dataset splits, signer-dependent vs. signer-independent), so absolute numbers are not directly comparable. Our method targets a **signer-independent** protocol on WLASL-300 and emphasises accuracy *and* deployability.

Method	Backbone	Temporal	Attention	Dataset	Protocol	Top-1
CNN + LSTM Attn [1]	+ MobileNetV2	LSTM	Yes	WLASL-100	SD	84.65%
PoseFormer [4]	PoseFormer	1D-TCConv + SA	+ MHA	WLASL / AUTS	/ SD	61.40%
SIGNGRAPH [16]	ResGCN	2D-TCConv	No	WLASL-1000	SD	72.73%
Ours	MobileNetV3	BiLSTM	Bahdanau	WLASL-300	SI	67.46%
Efficiency (ours): Params = 3.62 M, GFLOPs = 0.93, Peak mem. = 40.09 MB						

Notes. SD: signer-dependent; SI: signer-independent; SA: self-attention; MHA: multi-head attention. As many prior results are reported on different WLASL subsets (*e.g.*, 100 / 1000) and typically under signer-*dependent* settings, they are not directly comparable to our signer-*independent* WLASL-300 evaluation. Within this stricter protocol and sub-1 GFLOP regime, our model offers a state-of-the-art accuracy–efficiency trade-off.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

5.1 Conclusion

We presented a lightweight, word-level sign language recognition framework that couples a MobileNetV3-Large backbone for spatial encoding with a two-layer BiLSTM for temporal modelling and a frame-level Bahdanau attention module for adaptive focus. Under a signer-independent protocol on WLASL-300, the model attains **67.46%** Top-1 accuracy with a **14.07 MB** footprint and **0.93** GFLOPs, offering a favourable accuracy–efficiency trade-off that is suitable for real-time and edge deployment. Attention visualisations indicate that the network concentrates on discriminative motion phases, improving interpretability without materially increasing computational cost. Overall, the results show that a compact spatial backbone paired with targeted sequence modelling and attention can deliver competitive performance under stricter evaluation while remaining practical to deploy.

5.2 Future Work

Future work will focus on further compressing and accelerating the model while preserving accuracy, including structured pruning, low-rank factorisation, post-training quantisation to INT8/INT4, and knowledge distillation aligned to mobile NPU. We will extend the data pipeline with SLR-specific augmentations—for example, hand-region jitter, motion-blur simulation, and illumination shifts—and explore semi- and self-supervised pre-training on unlabelled sign video. To increase robustness under occlusion and signer variability, we plan to investigate

lightweight multimodal fusion using RGB with optical flow and keypoints from hands and face. On the temporal side, we will study learnable keyframe selection, monotonic or segmental attention, and efficient temporal Transformers to better capture long-range dependencies without sacrificing latency. Finally, we will broaden evaluation to cross-corpus transfer and domain shift settings, introduce few-shot signer adaptation, and report end-to-end latency, memory usage, and energy on representative mobile devices to facilitate reproducible, deployment-oriented assessment; in parallel, we will examine fairness across signers, lighting conditions, and backgrounds, and release code, trained weights, and an evaluation suite to support transparent comparison under signer-independent protocols.

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